

THE USE OF GAMES IN TEACHING ENGLISH TO UNIVERSITY STUDENTS AS A SECOND LANGUAGE

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***Annotation:** The paper discusses the features of the interactive teaching methods use in the English language classroom, provides their examples and analyzes the methods of their implementation. Special attention is paid to the use of these technologies in students' foreign language speech activity.*

***Key words:** the method of cognitive games, the interactive method, communicative methodology, Project-based learning*

To create an emotional situation in the classroom, well-chosen examples from literature, feature films, and personal experiences of the teacher are important. The brightness of the narrative, the emotional assessment of the teacher excite the interest of students, both to individual issues of the topic and to the material in general. The most common among the methods of this group, it is advisable, in our opinion, to use in English classes:

- a method of creating a situation of novelty of educational material. It provides for the definition of new knowledge in the teaching process, the creation of an atmosphere of moral satisfaction from intellectual work. The feeling of enriching knowledge encourages students to self-improvement.
- the method of cognitive games. It contributes to the creation of an emotionally elevated atmosphere, the assimilation of the material with the help of an emotionally saturated form of its reproduction. Cognitive games (business, role-playing, situational) model life situations, people's relationships, the interaction of things, phenomena. They can be the main or auxiliary form of the educational process. The

developing effect is achieved through improvisation, the natural manifestation of students' free creative forces. In the educational sense, the game helps students to overcome uncertainty, promotes self-affirmation, identification of their strengths and capabilities.

The game is the most accessible type of activity for students, a way of processing impressions received from the outside world. The game clearly shows the peculiarities of thinking and imagination, emotionality, activity, developing the need for communication.

An interesting game increases the student's activity level, and he can solve a more difficult task than in a regular lesson. But this does not mean that all classes should take place in the form of a game.

The game is only one of the methods, and it gives good results only in combination with others: listening, talking, reading and others.

The word interactive (translated from English inter - "mutual", act - "to act") means interaction. The interactive method is a way of interacting with students through conversation, dialogue [2].

Learning English is a complex, multifaceted process that requires regular and creative activity. It is considered by experts as one of the main directions of introducing a foreign language into the public environment, aimed at improving the level of proficiency, which is carried out taking into account the state of its proficiency and development [3].

It is important for a modern teacher to know the latest methods of teaching English, special teaching techniques and techniques in order to optimally choose one or another teaching method in accordance with the level of knowledge, needs and interests of students. Teaching methods are not simple algorithmized units, their rational and motivated use in English classes requires a creative approach on the part of the teacher [4].

Modern communicative methodology offers a wide introduction of active non-standard methods and forms of work into the educational process for better conscious assimilation of the material. In practice, such forms of work turned out to

be quite effective: individual, pair, group and team work. Therefore, all exercises and tasks should be communicatively justified by the lack of information, choice and reaction (Information gap, choice, feedback). To fulfill them, students will need additional information, they will make certain efforts to assimilate it and thus will be able to organize their activities better and more effectively.

The most effective forms of pair and group work are:

- inner (outer) circles (inside / outside circles);
- brainstorming (brain storm);
- zigzag reading (jigsaw reading);
- exchange of opinions (think-pair-share);
- pair interviews (pair-interviews) and others.

One of the methods that provide English language teaching is the project method as a way to develop creativity, cognitive activity, independence. Projects can be divided into mono-projects, collective, oral-speech, specific, written and Internet projects. Working on the project is a multi-level approach to learning English, covering reading, listening, speaking and grammar. The project method promotes the development of active independent thinking of students and orients them to joint research work.

Project-based learning is relevant because it teaches students to cooperate, educates such ethical values as mutual assistance and the ability to empathize, forms creative abilities and activates students.

The project method implements differentiated, individually creative and actively effective approaches in teaching. The project can have a research, search, creative (creative), predictive, analytical and game character. The basis of the project method is based on the interests and wishes of the participants. The author of the project as a special educational task can be both a teacher and a student (if he expresses his proposal). Since the project is planned and implemented by a student independently or by a group of students, this method provides favorable conditions for activating their responsibility, forming partnerships between the project performers and the teacher.

The following games provide for mastering the vocabulary on the studied topic and common words.

“Grab a minute” is a game in which a student is given 1 minute to represent a term written on an interactive map. It is necessary to provide more information about this subject/term, its meaning, use, and the like. The winner is the student who has provided the most complete and coherent information about the subject or term indicated in the card.

Knowledge test: Vocabulary from a specific topic combined with grammar. A good way to consolidate the material passed.

Game features: improve the skills of rapid response, critical thinking.

“An item description” is a game in which it is necessary to describe a word or phrase indicated on interactive maps without naming the root of the word and without using gestures. At the same time, the other groups play an active role, which must guess the word.

Knowledge test: Vocabulary from a specific topic combined with grammar. Can be used as a Warm up activity.

Features of the game: rapid response skills are improved, the search for synonyms in English is activated. Direct communicative contact with the group has a positive effect on the relationship within the group.

“Chain story” is a game of logic, a manifestation of imagination and individuality. The essence of the game is to continue the story of the previous student.

Knowledge test: Vocabulary with a specific topic and general vocabulary combined with grammar.

Features of the game: improve the skills of rapid reaction, logical thinking, increased attention, no less role is given to focusing on the plot of the story, helps to develop memory.

The above games can be held in the second part of the lesson to increase the activity of students and improve the perception of information. They do not require significant training and depend on the theoretical level of students' knowledge. From

the examples given, we see that there are a large number of forms of interactive classes. The biggest mistake of a teacher is the use of one teaching method or the choice of one form of conducting an interactive task. It should be remembered that the channels of information perception are not one-sided, therefore, various forms should be involved.

Analyzing the above material, we can conclude that the use of interactive forms and methods in the implementation of a personality-oriented approach in teaching English can practically increase the amount of conversational practice in the classroom, are interesting for students, help to assimilate the material and use it in further classes, perform didactic and developmental functions. Thus, the teacher becomes a mentor of independent educational, cognitive and creative activity of students. Having many advantages, one should also keep in mind the disadvantages: with frequent use, the perception of interactive games becomes mechanical, loses creative interest, therefore it is necessary to diversify games and combine interactive teaching methods with traditional ones.

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